

DARIAH CoARA Progress Report and Action Plan (2025-2027)

Authors: Françoise Gouzi & Toma Tasovac

Introduction

In November 2022, DARIAH ERIC (Digital Research Infrastructure for Arts and Humanities) became a founding member of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)¹, a pan-European initiative to reform research assessment by prioritising qualitative, context-sensitive evaluation over narrow journal-based metrics. Since then, DARIAH has actively pursued initiatives that align with CoARA's principles, including open peer review, the recognition of non-traditional research outputs, and the development of indicators and policies for assessing infrastructural contributions. This Progress Report and Action Plan (2025–2027) brings these strands together by both documenting achievements from 2022–2024 and setting out the priorities for 2025–2027.

The rationale for DARIAH's involvement in CoARA is clear: conventional proxies like Journal Impact Factor or h-index neither capture the diversity of outputs typical of A&H nor the collaborative, infrastructural labour on which digital research depends. A large and growing literature shows both the limits of metric-centric assessment and the benefits of qualitative, criteria-led peer evaluation (see for instance, Langfeldt, Reymert, and Aksnes 2021; Williams 2020; Smit and Hessels 2021; Lewandowska, Kulczycki, and Ochsner 2023). DARIAH's position paper on *The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform* has emphasized that critical contributions to research infrastructures, such as developing digital tools, curating born-digital data, and providing training, remain undervalued in many countries and many institutions that still use conventional evaluation systems focusing on journal publications and citation counts. Such traditional metrics often reward individual, monographic outputs and high-impact journal placements, while overlooking collaborative and infrastructural work. Acknowledging this misalignment, DARIAH has argued that “policy makers, funding agencies, and research-performing institutions should recognise the significant potential of thematic research infrastructures to serve as enablers of, and

¹ CoARA is a collective of organisations at European level committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated. (see About <https://coara.eu/>)

contributors to, a research assessment system that truly values the multiplicity of ways in which scientific knowledge is created, accumulated, integrated, disseminated and preserved.” (Tasovac et al. 2023).

For DARIAH, research assessment reform is not only an aspiration or a scholarly debate: it is also a policy mandate. The CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (2022) commits signatories to recognize the diversity of contributions and careers; to base assessment primarily on qualitative peer review; and to avoid the inappropriate use of rankings and journal-level metrics. Aligning organisational practice with these principles is essential for infrastructures like DARIAH, whose operations depend on sustained contributions in data stewardship, tool development, training, and community governance — activities systematically under-recognised in traditional assessment regimes.

DARIAH’s approach is consistent with evolving European guidance on monitoring and evaluating research infrastructures (RIs): ESFRI and the European Commission emphasise balanced indicator frameworks for RI performance (combining quantitative KPIs with qualitative evidence), while the OECD highlights the need for evaluation systems that support openness, societal value, and resilience (see ESFRI 2022²; OECD 2023³). Embedding these expectations internally, while contributing evidence and practice models externally, positions DARIAH as both beneficiary and driver of assessment reform.

With this Progress Report and Action Plan, DARIAH provides a roadmap for implementing its commitments under the CoARA agreement and for sustaining momentum in research assessment reform. By amplifying contributions from its member countries and partners, DARIAH aims to help shape a research assessment ecosystem that truly values openness, collaboration, and the wide array of scholarly contributions that characterise arts and humanities research.

This Progress Report and Action Plan is structured as follows:

Section 1 provides an overview of DARIAH as a research infrastructure facing the challenges of enhancing and supporting digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities.

Section 2 describes selected activities DARIAH undertook between 2022 and 2024 implementing specific quantitative indicators, Open Science tools and services, and contributing to specific projects or networks that are relevant to the reform of research assessment.

Section 3 presents the DARIAH Action Plan encompassing strategy for community engagement for the period of 2025-2027.

² ESFRI. (2022). ESFRI Landmark Monitoring Guide (Public). European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_LM-Monitoring_Guide_Public.pdf

³ OECD. 2023. OECD Science, Technology and Innovation Outlook 2023: Enabling Transitions in Times of Disruption. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/0b55736e-en>.

Section 4 details the process and stakeholders to be involved internally to monitor and auto-evaluate the DARIAH Action Plan so as to report in a transparent way the progress, and expected outcomes to both the DARIAH community and the CoARA members and community.

1. Context: DARIAH and the arts & humanities

DARIAH, established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2014 and recognized as an ESFRI Landmark since 2016, is a distributed infrastructure whose mission is to “empower research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge about culture and society”. It is a membership-based organization, currently composed of 23 member countries across Europe and 17 Cooperating Partners in ten non-member countries, committed to sharing resources, tools, and knowledge. DARIAH has previously chaired and currently vice-chairs the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster ([SSHOC](#)), a consortium of thematic research infrastructures contributing to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In all these roles, DARIAH has been strongly committed to Open Research, working to bridge the gap between the core principles of Open Science (transparency, inclusivity, innovation) and everyday practices in a wide variety of arts and humanities disciplines.

It is important to note that research infrastructures (RIs) are not research-performing institutions like universities, research institutes, or laboratories. While research-performing institutions conduct original research (generating new knowledge and scholarly outputs), research infrastructures primarily provide the resources, services, and frameworks that enable such research to take place. According to the European Commission, RIs are facilities that “provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation” (European Commission 2019). In other words, an RI’s role is to enhance the conditions for research rather than to directly produce research results. RIs offer access to data, tools, technologies, expertise, and collaborative networks that facilitate discovery and innovation across disciplines. Their mission is to ensure that researchers have the necessary tools, be it digital repositories, high-performance computing, specialized knowledge bases, or methodological guidelines, to advance their work efficiently and collaboratively.

Even though DARIAH itself does not primarily conduct research, many of its core activities involve processes that require careful evaluation and assessment. For example, DARIAH regularly reviews and selects proposals for the establishment of Working Groups, which bring together researchers and practitioners to develop methods, tools, and resources for the arts and humanities. DARIAH also allocates funding through its Working Group grants and Thematic Calls, which support innovative projects that align with its mission. Since 2016, DARIAH has organised an Annual Event, a scholarly conference where researchers submit proposals for presentations, workshops, and panels, which undergo a review process to ensure academic quality and relevance. More recently, DARIAH has expanded its role by

launching *Transformations*, a diamond, open access, peer-reviewed journal for documenting various methodological and research activities in arts and humanities, including data gathering and processing, annotation and modeling, analysis and interpretation. Beyond these institutional activities, DARIAH's staff also actively contributes to the research community by participating in collaborative projects, delivering conference presentations and workshops, and publishing scholarly papers. Taken together, all these activities demonstrate that facilitating research requires rigorous, transparent, and well-documented assessment practices to ensure that resources are allocated effectively and that the initiatives research infrastructures support meet high academic and professional standards. In practice, this means DARIAH applies many of the same principles that CoARA promotes, such as peer review backed by clear qualitative criteria, and recognition of diverse contributions, in its internal processes.

2. DARIAH Progress Report (2022-2024)

Between 2022 and 2024, DARIAH undertook a wide range of activities that directly or indirectly contribute to the reform of research assessment. These efforts span technical, operational, and policy levels and illustrate how a thematic research infrastructure can act both as a testing ground and as a driver of change. In this period, DARIAH invested in developing robust self-assessment mechanisms, articulated strategic policies for services and data, engaged in European-level collaborations such as EOOSC, expanded its Open Science services, and contributed actively to debates on peer review and evaluation reform.

This section highlights six main strands of activity:

- 2.1 Developing a self-assessment process and indicators
- 2.2 Providing clear framework and pathways for science policy and services
- 2.3 Managing and sharing knowledge and resources
- 2.4 Cross-cluster collaboration within the European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC)
- 2.5 Contributing to Open Science by exploring news models and practices
- 2.6 Supporting changes in peer review practices

2.1 Developing a self-assessment process and indicators

As with all research infrastructures, DARIAH is itself subject to monitoring and assessment. Moreover, "in-kind" contributions form part of the funding model of distributed RIs, which means that measuring engagement and impact is essential not only for accountability but also for sustainability.

Since 2019, DARIAH has systematically collected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to build a longitudinal, evidence-based picture of its value. These indicators are organised into three high-level categories (Usage, Effectiveness, and Impact) and draw on data from national consortia as well as from European and international contexts.

- **Usage** (the DARIAH User Barometer) comprises 7 quantitative indicators tracking DARIAH's scale and reach:
 - DARIAH Indicator 1: Number of Members and Observers
 - DARIAH Indicator 2: Number of Collaborating Institutions (in national nodes and Cooperating Partners)
 - DARIAH Indicator 3: Number of central staff
 - DARIAH Indicator 4: Number of contributors
 - DARIAH Indicator 5: Number of face-to-face interactions
 - DARIAH Indicator 6: Number of platform interactions
 - DARIAH Indicator 7: Number of training resources.
- **Effectiveness** is based on the development and progress against the current DARIAH Strategic Action Plan, as validated by the DARIAH General Assembly and monitored by the STRAPL monitoring group:
 - DARIAH Indicator 8: Delivery against the Strategic Action Plan.
- **Impact** is based on 2 quantitative indicators:
 - DARIAH Indicator 9: Number of publications,
 - DARIAH Indicator 10: Amount of funding leveraged

To complement the quantitative indicators, DARIAH produces annual [Impact Case Studies](#) - (three per year). These qualitative narratives highlight the diversity of activities supported by DARIAH, ranging from the outcomes of national consortia and working groups to the practices of individual researchers in digital A&H.

Together, the KPIs and Impact Case Studies provide a balanced framework: quantitative signals allow for long-term monitoring of trends, while qualitative cases capture the richness of DARIAH's contribution and the often-invisible work of infrastructures. In 2022, DARIAH also undertook an exercise to align its KPIs with the ESFRI Landmark Monitoring Guide (ESFRI 2022), ensuring that its approach reflects emerging European standards for RI evaluation.

2.2 Providing clear framework and pathways for science policy and services

DARIAH's role as a policy actor is reflected in a series of strategic documents that articulate standards for how research data, services, and infrastructure contributions should be managed, shared, and evaluated. These policies provide frameworks that make assessment practices more transparent and reproducible:

- [DARIAH Data Policy](#) (2024) targets both data producers and data providers, encourages the use of open formats and community standards, and acknowledges the diversity of options for data publishing. It also makes concrete recommendations for publishing DARIAH-affiliated data in trustworthy repositories with the goal of making them discoverable through the OpenAIRE-Graph.
- [DARIAH Services Policy](#) (2023) defines the coordination and management of DARIAH's distributed infrastructure in terms of service offer and provision, and sets expectations for transparency, sustainability, and quality across the network.

- *The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper* (Tasovac et al. 2023) argues for the need to strengthen the evaluative cultures of research infrastructures in order to recognize the scholarly value of contributions that are often invisible in formal assessment. This foundational document positions DARIAH as an advocate for expanding the definition of scholarly value beyond traditional proxies such as journal impact factors and citation counts.

By codifying good practices in data and service management, as well as research assessment, DARIAH not only ensures internal coherence but also provides models that can be reused by funders, universities, and other RIs.

2.3 Managing and sharing knowledge and resources

As a broker for its members, DARIAH's mission is not only to coordinate contributions to shared services but also to make them discoverable, accessible, and reusable by the wider research community. Between 2022 and 2024, this mission was advanced by means of consolidated service portfolios, platforms and data collections:

- [DARIAH services](#) catalogue. A catalogue that distinguishes between Core services (owned by DARIAH-ERIC and essential to fulfilling its mission) and Community services (mature services provided by DARIAH partners).
- [SSH Open Marketplace](#). A discovery portal aggregating tools, services, training materials, datasets, and workflows for SSH. DARIAH uses the Marketplace to showcase its Tools & Services catalogue, offering researchers an easy entry point into EOSC
- [DARIAH OpenAIRE Gateway](#). A subset of the OpenAIRE Graph, harvesting publications, datasets, and software associated with DARIAH activities, thus making them more visible and citable.
- [DARIAH HAL Collection](#). A dedicated collection within the French HAL repository for A&H researchers to deposit outputs related to DARIAH.
- [DARIAH Zenodo Community](#). A curated collection of outputs arising from DARIAH Working Groups, Thematic Calls, National Consortia, and other collaborative activities.
- [DARIAH-Campus](#). DARIAH's flagship platform for training and capacity building, offering an open and curated collection of learning materials for digitally enabled arts and humanities research.

Together, these services constitute the backbone of an ecosystem in which contributions—whether scholarly publications, tools, datasets, or training materials—are not only produced but also properly registered, curated, evaluated, and reused.

2.4 Cross-cluster collaboration within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

Research infrastructures, such as DARIAH, play a crucial role in engaging the research community with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Within the [OSCARS project](#), DARIAH, as a SSHOC member and in close collaboration with the other [Science Clusters](#), leads the consolidation work needed to establish Clusters' services and data sources portfolio as a basis to deploy, not only narrative but also, actionable workflows in a researcher-focused EOSC infrastructure.

In this cross-cluster collaboration, the DARIAH-led approach to onboarding and integrated services has been recognised as crucial: *"the [DARIAH Services Policy](#), which is closely aligned with EOSC, has been shared with other research infrastructures beyond the Social Sciences and Humanities, both as inspiration for their own service management and in preparation for their contribution to the EOSC Federation".*⁴

2.5 Contributing to Open Science by exploring news models and practices

DARIAH has, since its foundation, fostered best practices in data management and reuse for arts and humanities researchers, as part of its commitment to Open Science. See, for instance, the [DARIAH Impact Case Study: An Open Science Voice for the Humanities – A Humanities Voice for Open Science](#). DARIAH is also a champion of domain-specific approaches to implementing Open Science: we aim to help understand and apply generic OS frameworks such as FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefits, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics), to the concrete situations and practices of the arts and humanities researchers.

Between 2022 and 2024, DARIAH's commitment to Open Science was advanced through:

- [Transformations: A DARIAH Journal](#). Launched in 2024 as a diamond open-access journal hosted on Episciences, this DARIAH core service prioritises reproducibility, methodological transparency, and the evaluation of non-traditional research outputs.
- [DARIAH Open Blog](#). Provides a venue for commentary, debate, and dissemination on Open Humanities, complementing peer-reviewed publications.
- [OpenMethods Metablog](#). Curates and disseminates information on DH methods and tools, addressing a gap in peer-reviewed coverage of European DH practices.

In parallel, the **DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group** organised workshops and produced guidelines that translate generic RDM/FAIR principles into practices suited to humanities research contexts. Collectively, these activities illustrate DARIAH's role as a platform for experimenting with Open Science models and translating them into domain-specific practices.

⁴<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/impact-case-studies/cross-cluster-collaboration-dariah-engaging-the-research-community-in-the-european-open-science-cloud-eosc/>

2.6 Supporting changes in peer review practices

Finally, DARIAH has contributed actively to debates and practices around peer review, a cornerstone of CoARA commitments by means of:

- Active membership of the COARA Working Group “Evaluating SSH globally” since 2024 and, especially, Task Group 3 which focuses on *ENRESSH principles and recommendations and their implementation*.
- Participation in the PALOMERA project contributing to actionable [recommendations](#) to support and coordinate aligned funder and institutional policies for OA books, with the overall objective of speeding up the transition to OA for books.
- Contribution to OPERASPlus [Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities](#) focused on building a new framework for evaluating innovative outputs and projects such as digital monographs, and other multimedia materials, datasets, software, and digital tools and platforms. The recognition and evaluation of diverse, non-traditional digital scholarly outputs in social sciences and humanities (SSH) are crucial for advancing inclusive and impactful research assessment practices.

By engaging in both policy development and practical implementation, DARIAH has positioned itself as a key actor in shaping new models of peer review. The emphasis on non-traditional outputs, such as datasets, software, and workflows, will play a particularly important role in the Action Plan for 2025-2027, which is described in more detail in the next section.

3. DARIAH Action Plan: 2025-2027

How is DARIAH addressing the 10 CoARA commitments (milestones)?

Building on the activities carried out in 2022–2024, the Action Plan (2025–2027) focuses on two priorities:

1. improving transparency and recognition of non-traditional research outputs in review and evaluation procedures; and
2. enhancing the visibility and value of research infrastructure contributions—including data, tools, services, collaborations, training, and events—across the European SSH community.

These actions are implemented in alignment with the ten CoARA commitments.

CoARA Commitment	Actions	Timeframe
1. Recognise the diversity of	→ <i>Transformations: A DARIAH Journal</i> embraces contributions from the broad spectrum of digital arts	June 2025

contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	and humanities as well as individual humanistic disciplines that rely on the use of digital tools, methods and assets. Publication of first issue on Workflows in 2025. → Presentation of a paper “Building an Evaluation Framework for Innovative Research Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities”, in collaboration with IBL-PAN/OPERASPlus in DH Benelux 2025 (Wnuk, Maryl, Gouzi 2025)	June 2025
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	Improving transparency and recognition of non-traditional research outputs in reviewing activities and procedures. Building a Peer review framework for research outputs (Task 7.4 of ATRIUM Project led by DARIAH). The goal of this deliverable is to develop an evaluation framework for open peer review assessment of non-traditional research outputs as a contribution toward maximising the quality and impact of arts and humanities research in Europe in line with CoARA.	Dec. 2025
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	→ Assess <i>Transformations: A DARIAH Journal</i> in Diamond Assessment tools DOAJ and DOAS → Develop appropriate ‘ DARIAH Citation scheme ’ to allow DARIAH and other RIs to be properly cited in all research outputs that have benefited from RI’s support. This citation scheme is to be included in our DARIAH Resource Guidelines (ongoing process) and linked to DARIAH Services and Data Policy.	2026 2026
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	DARIAH has never used rankings of research organizations in any of its internal assessment procedures.	
5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as needed to achieve the planned organisational changes	Regular report of the changes and achieved actions within DARIAH internal bodies (Board of Directors, Scientific Board, WGs, JRC)	2025-2027

<p>6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes</p>	<p>→ Linked to commitment 2, produce a set of 6 evaluation grids (data papers; workflow papers; training materials; visual representations including 3D digital editions; Software and code; Digital scholarly editions) and implemented in <i>Transformations Journal</i> with emphasis on data availability and reusability.</p> <p>→ Create a specific Data Policy⁵ for <i>Transformations Journal</i> encompassing clear requirements for both authors and reviewers</p> <p>→ Conduct a thorough analysis of current evaluation and review procedures for both the DARIAH Annual Event and <i>Transformations</i>, and propose concrete measures to improve their quality, transparency, and alignment</p>	<p>June 2026</p> <p>Spring 2026</p> <p>Autumn 2026</p>
<p>7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use</p>	<p>→ Presentation of <i>Transformations</i>, Diamond Journal for Archeology community (in CAA conference 2025, Athens)</p> <p>→ Keynote at RESSH2025: The Challenges of Research Assessment: What Research Infrastructures Have Got to Do With It?</p> <p>→ Organise workshops to support authors and reviewers on how to implement best practices in open peer review (for non-traditional outputs)</p> <p>→ Promote and share resources (guidelines, training material) created under the peer review framework at European level (EDCH - European Diamond Capacity Hub/OPERAS, CLARIN and CESSDA)</p>	<p>June 2025</p> <p>May 2025</p> <p>2026-2027</p> <p>2026-2027</p>
<p>8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition</p>	<p>→ Organise workshops and webinars across DARIAH Working Groups and beyond to share experiences, disseminate reform practices and showcase assessment approaches that acknowledge a broad range of contributions to both research and research infrastructures.</p>	<p>2026-2027</p>
<p>9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the</p>	<p>Communicate efforts and outcomes</p> <p>→ with DARIAH communities (National members, WGs, Annual Event Audience)</p>	<p>2025-2027</p>

⁵ See for example this generic policy for journals: Romain Feret, Françoise Gouzi, Sandra Guignonis, Hlne Jouguet, Nicolas Larrouse, et al.. *Guidelines for journals that wish to establish a "data policy" related to their publications*. Research Data College of the French Committee for Open Science. 2021, 10 p. ([hal-03640532](#)).

Principles and implementation of the Commitments	<p>→ with specific projects (GraspOS/OPERAS)</p> <p>→ with specific sisters RIs (CLARIN, CESSDA)</p> <p>→ with CoARA WGs ('Evaluating SSH' and 'Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment')</p> <p>→ Disseminate and share the Action Plan within the national consortia as key and primary DARIAH stakeholders to encourage them to take up these issues and support the implementation (or replication) of the Action Plan at the national level.</p>	
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research	<p>→ Presentation of a poster 'Building a Peer Review Framework for Non-Traditional Research Outputs' (DH2025 July, Lisbon)</p> <p>→ As a contribution to TG3 (CoARA WG 'Evaluating SSH'), review the ENRESSH principles and recommendations and create actionable guidance for assessment of SSH research.</p>	<p>July 2025</p> <p>According to CoARA WG 'Evaluating SSH' specific Timeline</p>

4. Monitoring and evaluation

Effective monitoring will ensure that the Action Plan is both transparent and accountable. DARIAH will establish a regular cycle of reporting and review throughout 2025–2027. Key elements include:

- **Internal review:** Biannual updates within DARIAH governance bodies (Board of Directors, Scientific Board, Joint Research Committee).
- **Documentation:** Clear tracking of activities and achievements, with interim progress reports.
- **External transparency:** Public communication of results and achievements including open access to documentation and updates.

Conclusion

This Progress Report and Action Plan underscores DARIAH's commitment to embedding the CoARA principles in practice. A central element of this commitment has been the successful launch and the publication of the first issue of *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal*, a diamond open access venue designed to provide rigorous peer review for non-traditional research outputs such as datasets, workflows, and training materials. By foregrounding reproducibility, transparency, and methodological innovation, *Transformations* not only strengthens DARIAH's service portfolio but also offers a concrete model for how infrastructures can sustain new forms of scholarly communication and assessment (Tasovac 2025). DARIAH remains committed to refining its evaluation procedures, developing innovative peer review frameworks, and improving its own assessment practices as part of a push towards a more inclusive and sustainable evaluative culture for arts and humanities in Europe and beyond.

References

European Commission. 2019. What are Research Infrastructures? (Research & Innovation strategy factsheet). Brussels: European Commission

Feret, R., Gouzi, F., Guignon, S., Jouguet, H., Larrousse, N. et al. 2021. Guidelines for journals that wish to establish a “data policy” related to their publications. Research Data College of the French Committee for Open Science <hal-03640532>

Langfeldt, L., Reymert, I. and Aksnes, D. W. 2021. “The Role of Metrics in Peer Assessments.” *Research Evaluation* 30(1): 112–126. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvaa032>.

Lewandowska, K., Kulczycki, E., and Ochsner, M. 2023. “Evaluation of the Arts in Performance-Based Research Funding Systems: An International Perspective.” *Research Evaluation* 32(1): 19–31. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvac017>.

Maryl, M., Wnuk, M., Gouzi, F., & Umerle, T. 2024. Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 4.1) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14221728>

Smit, J. P., and Hessels, L. 2021. “The Production of Scientific and Societal Value in Research Evaluation: A Review of Societal Impact Assessment Methods.” *Research Evaluation* 30(3): 323–335. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvab002>.

Tasovac, T., Romary, L., Tóth-Czifra, E., Ackermann, R.C, Alves, D. et al. 2023. The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper. <hal-04136772>

Tasovac, T. 2025. Introducing *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal*. *Transformations. A DARIAH Journal*, vol. 1, 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.46298/transformations.15787>

Williams, K. 2020. “Playing the Fields: Theorizing Research Impact and Its Assessment.” *Research Evaluation* 29(2): 191–202. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvaa001>